

First record of *Exentricus planicornis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1836) (Heteroptera: Miridae) for Hungary

Berend Aukema, Betty van Middelkoop & Ruud van Middelkoop

Van Kellstraat 25, NL-6721 VT Bennekom, Netherlands

E-mail: berendaukema@outlook.com ORCID iD: 0000-0003-4268-9777

ABSTRACT: The first record of *Exentricus planicornis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1836) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Miridae) for Hungary is reported. Details about the distribution and biology of the species are summarised from the literature.

KEYWORDS: *Exentricus planicornis*, first record, distribution, Hungary, biology.

Exentricus planicornis (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1836) is a Palaearctic species known from Europe, North Africa and Asia. In Europe it is listed from Bulgaria, Byelorrussia, the Czech Republic, France, Germany, Italy, Kosovo, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland and Ukraine, in North Africa from Morocco, and in Asia from Armenia, Azerbaijan, North China, Georgia, Iran, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Russia (from West Siberia up to and including the Far East) and Turkey (Aukema, 2018; Dioli & van der Heyden, 2022). The record from Austria in Atkinson (1890) can not be attributed to one of

present days countries of the former Austrian Empire. No more findings were since than made in Austria (Rabitsch, 2004).

Here the first record for Hungary is reported: the second and third author collected a male (Fig. 1) and a fifth instar larva (Fig. 2) on 04.06.2023 from rose (*Rosa spec.*) near Tiszaszölös in the province of Jász-Nagykun-Szolnok (47.5493°N 20.7327°W). The male is deposited in the collection of the first author.

Exentricus planicornis lives zoophytophagous

To cite this article: Aukema, B., van Middelkoop, B. & van Middelkoop, R., 2025, First record of *Exentricus planicornis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1836) (Heteroptera: Miridae) for Hungary, *J.Het.Turk.*, 7(1):8-10

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15313166

To link to this article: <https://www.j-het.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/V71-A3.pdf>

Received: Dec 3, 2024; **Revised:** Feb 19, 2025; **Accepted:** Feb 19, 2025; **Published online:** May 7, 2025

on Rosaceae (*Rosa*) and Fabaceae to aphids as food source. The last adults (*Cytisus* and *Genista*) (Wachmann et al., 2004). Mandery (2012) documented its biology and life cycle on French Rose (*Rosa gallica*) in Bayern, South Germany. The first instars were found in the beginning of May and became adult after three weeks. Larval instars feed on sap from the young shoots and adults switch

to aphids as food source. The last adults were observed at the end of June. Simon (2022) collected the species further north in Rheinland-Pfalz in Germany on Burnet Rose (*Rosa spinosissima*), larval instars at the end of April and an adult female in the first week of July. According to Wachmann et al. (2004) adults are mainly be found in July and August.

Figure 1. Male of *Excentricus planicornis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1836), Hungary, Province Jász-Nagykun-Szolnok, near Tiszaszölös, 04.06.2023 (Photo: R. van Middelkoop).

Figure 2. Fifth instar larva of *Excentricus planicornis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1836), Hungary, Province Jász-Nagykun-Szolnok, near Tiszaszölös, 04.06.2023 (Photo: R. van Middelkoop).

REFERENCES

- Atkinson, E.T., 1890, Catalogue of the Insecta. No. 2. Order Rhynchota, Suborder Hemiptera -Heteroptera. Family Capsidae. *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bengal*, 58, Part 2, Supplement 1: 25-199.
- Aukema, B. (ed.), 2018, *Catalogue of the Palae-arctic Heteroptera*. Available on: <https://catpalhet.linnaeus.naturalis.nl> [Accessed; 01.12.2024].
- Dioli, P., van der Heyden, T., 2022, Plant bugs (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Miridae) new in Albania and Kosovo, *Heteroptera Poloniae – Acta Faunistica*, 16: 3-6.
- Mandery, K., 2012, Die Dickfühler-Weichwanze *Excentricus planicornis* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1836) im FFH-Gebiet "ehemaliger Standortübungsplatz Ebern", Lkr. Haßberge - einmalig in Deutschland (Heteroptera: Miridae), *Galatea*, 28: 29-42.
- Rabitsch, W., 2004. Annotations to a checklist of the Heteroptera (Insecta) of Austria, *Annalen des Naturhistorischen Museums in Wien*, 105 B: 453-492.
- Simon, H., 2020, 4. Nachtrag zum Verzeichnis der Wanzen in Rheinland-Pfalz (Insecta: Heteroptera), *Fauna Flora Rheinland-Pfalz*, 14 (2): 659-686.
- Wachmann, E., Melber, A., Deckert, J., 2004, Wanzen 2. *Tierwelt Deutschlands*, 75: 1-294.